

Research Article

Comparative study of TSP, Inhalable Particles and Respirable Particles in Urban and Rural Areas in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Atmospheric environmental problems which had previously received scanty attention in Nigeria have become a subject of increasing National Significance over the two years. In this study the TSP, Inhalable and Respirable fraction were captured in ten locations in Sapele and five locations in Obaretin (rural) area gravimetrically between December 2008 and October 2009 using programmable Air check XR 5000 High volume sampler model 210-5000, with glass filter and respirable foam. The result showed that the mean TSP, Inhalable and Respirable fractions were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in Urban than Rural. Also, the urban were more likely to be above the limit set by the Federal Ministry of Environment.

Keywords: Urban Area, Rural area, TSP, Inhalable Particles and Respirable Particles.

Introduction:

The research on the quality of air in rural area and urban area in Nigeria is very minute. Available data mostly delineate rural atmosphere as more pristine than urban or industrial area (Okuo 2004, Fang et al, 2000, Hoek et al 1997, Mone et al 1995, Roosli et al 200, Darlington et al 1997, Brook et al, 1997, Keary et al, 1998, Harrison et al 2001). The sudden upsurge in rural particulate matter concentration can be adduced to the transportation of particles from polluted urban or industrial areas. (Muller 1999). Grima et al, 2002 suggested that the increased particulate matter concentration in urban may be influenced by long range transport from rural locations.

In Nigeria, the difference between the particulate matter generated in urban area and rural area was significance and noticeable (Okuo 2004). The major source of particulate matter in rural area is biomass burning while the major sources of particulate matter are vehicular related emission and gas flaring waste incineration (Sillanpaia et al 2005, Ward et al 2006, Okuo et al 2005, Ukpebor et al 2006).

According to aero dynamic diameter, the particulate matter can be classified into inhalable particles (PM_{10}) and respirable particle ($Pm_{2.5}$). The inhalable particle has the tendency of being expectorated when inhale while the respirable particles lodge in the lung capillaries and alveoli, causing the slowing down the exchange of oxygen and carbon dioxide in the blood, causing shortness of breath. The people most sensitive to these conditions include those with heart problems or respiratory diseases like emphysema, bronchitis asthma, the elderly and the children.

There are several studies that have linked particulate with health effect (Dockery 2001, Lighly et al, 2000; Curtis et al 2006, Givynn et al 2000, Pope et al 2002, Donalson et al 2002, Arden et al 2006, Vonklot et al 2002, Wilson and Suh (1997), Samet et all 2000).

The objective of this study is to compare the particulate matter (TSP, Inhalable and respirable particle in urban area and rural area in Nigeria.

Methodology**Sampling****Sampling Location:**

This study was conducted in ten different locations in Urban area (Sapele) and five different rural locations (Obaretin) both oil producing communities. The town Sapele is situated in the south- south geopolitical region of

Nigeria. It was once an integral part of the old Western Region of Nigeria. It is presently a part of Delta State of Nigeria created in August 27, 1991. This study area is located within the co-ordinates of latitude $N05^{\circ}50'0''$ – $N05^{\circ}56'0''$ Longitude $E005^{\circ}37'0''$ - $E005^{\circ}44'0''$. The study area has a total area of 165.25 square kilometer and with a population of 136,800(NPC2005/06)

Sapele is located near the junction of Jamieson and Ethiope rivers and about 80miles (144kilometers) from the sea. Sapele is one of the first-rate wood industry areas in this region. However, it is a commercial City with four petroleum and allied industries. The climate is tropical with two distinct seasons, wet and dry.

The major activities of the people of Sapele that generates particulate pollution are usually bush burning as a pre-planting preparation, combustion of solid wastes as a means of waste disposal, gas- flaring, resuspension of dust from unpaved roads and the production of charcoal which involves the burning of wood in an open space from dawn till dusk in six different locations in the city.

Obaretin is situated in Ikpoba- Okha L.G.A of Edo State, Nigeria. The study area is located within the co-ordinates of latitude $N06^{\circ}09'35.8''$ - $N06^{\circ}09'46.9''$, Longitude $E005^{\circ}38'30.4''$ - $E005^{\circ}38'53.8''$. The rural community is sparsely distributed with a population estimate of few thousand inhabitants. The settlement is situated along the main road with a thick rubber plantation. It has a population of about 850 (NPC 2000). The rural dwellers engage themselves in farming, hunting, rubber tapping and rural intra- transportation due to the accessibility of the community to the main road. Also the people engage in cassava processing, smoking of fishes, and their major way of waste disposal is by burning. The main road that leads to the community is untarred. All these afore- mentioned activities, are veritable generators of particulate matter in the environment.

Table 1: Sampling location in Sapele

S/N	SITE CODE	CO-ORDINATES	SITE DESCRIPTION
1.	SP. MV	$N05^{\circ}51'53.5''$ $E005^{\circ}41'39.0''$	The site was created at the Mechanic Village (Shell road)
2.	SP. SG	$N05^{\circ}51'025''$ $E005^{\circ}44'37.4''$	This site was created at the Songhai.
3.	SP.NOR	$N05^{\circ}51'06.3''$ $E005^{\circ}44'45.4''$	The site was created at the new Ogorode Road.
4.	SP.RH	$N05^{\circ}51'33.1''$ $E005^{\circ}43'06.4''$	The site was created in residential houses in Amoukpe Area
5.	SP.OJ	$N05^{\circ}53'24.8''$ $E005^{\circ}40'41.9''$	The site was created in Olympia Junction
6.	SP.SM	$N05^{\circ}54'05.9''$ $E005^{\circ}41'38.9''$	The site was created at Sapele Market
7.	SP.IA	$N05^{\circ}55'16.8''$ $E005^{\circ}38'48.5''$	The site was created at the Industrial Area.
8.	SP.NER	$N05^{\circ}51'01.9''$ $E005^{\circ}43'37.8''$	The site was created at New Eku Road
9.	SP.SWR	$N05^{\circ}52'28.6''$ $E005^{\circ}42'07.8''$	The site was created at Sapele Warri Road
10.	SP.OK	$N05^{\circ}52'27.0''$ $E005^{\circ}43'40.7''$	The site was created at Okireghwere.

Table 2: Obaretin monitoring sites and their co-ordinates

S/N	Side Code	Co-ordinates	Site Descriptions
1	RH _A	$N06^{\circ}9'43.3''$ $E005^{\circ}8'49.2''$	Mud house detached kitchen unceiled roof
2	RH _B	$N06^{\circ}09'46.9''$ $E005^{\circ}38'44.7''$	Mud house detached kitchen unceiled roof
3	RH _C	$N06^{\circ}09'46.9''$ $E005^{\circ}38'48.1''$	Mud house detached kitchen, unceiled roof
4	RH _D	$N06^{\circ}09'40.0''$ $E005^{\circ}38'53.8''$	Mud house detached kitchen unceiled roof
5	RH _E	$N06^{\circ}09'35.8''$ $E005^{\circ}38'0.4''$	Mud house detached kitchen unceiled roof

Figure 1: Map of Obaretin and their various sampling locations.

Figure 2: Map of Sapele Reflecting the various sampling locations

Sampling Procedure for TSP

Airborne particulate matter was collected on a Whatman glass fiber filter using a portable SKC Air Check XR 5000 high volume Gravimetric Sampler for one year (December 2008 – October 2009). The Sampler was placed at a height of between 1.5m-2.0m. The sampling unit consists of a gas pump, a filter- holder- manifold connected to the sampling pump by a Teflon tube, with a gas flow rate meter of 1000 to 5000ml/min, used to measure the flow rate during sampling.

Before sampling, all unloaded glass fiber filters were dried in a desiccator at room temperature.

The particulates were collected on the pre-weighed filter by pumping 2000ml/min (2l/min) volume of air through it for eight (8) hours. After sampling, the loaded filters were again desiccated and reweighed to determine the final weight. The concentration of the total suspended particulate (TSP) in the air was determined from the difference in weight of the filter paper after and before sampling, the duration of sampling and the flow rate. (Shaw 1987, UNEP / WHO, 1994)

$$TSP(\mu g / m^3) = \frac{\text{Final weight (mg)} - \text{initial weight (mg)} \times 1000}{\text{Flow rate (m}^3 / \text{min)} \times \text{sampling period}}$$

Sampling Procedure for Respirable and Inhalable Fraction

SKC Aircheck XR5000 high volume Gravimetric sampler and the I.O.M multi fraction dust sampler (Institute of Occupational Medicine). The I.O.M (Institute of occupation Medicine Edinburgh) multi fraction dust sampler uses 25mm diameter filter for inhalable dust sampling it is a flexible sample head which can be with foam to give a respirable measurement.

The filter and cassette rear was pre-weighed to determine the initial respirable dust, while the filter, foam and whole cassette together was pre-weighed to determine the initial inhalable. After sampling, the filter foam, and the whole cassette together was re-weighed to determine the inhalable fraction. Then the whole cassette was split in order to weigh the cassette rear and filter only to determine the final weight of the respirable fractions. The particles were collected at a flow rate of 2L/min for eight hours and the sampler was placed between the height of 1.5m-2.0m. The difference between the final weights and initial weight is the amount of respirable and inhalable dust collected.

The concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was calculated by

$$\frac{\text{Final weight (mg)} - \text{initial weight (mg)} \times 1000}{\text{Flow rate (m}^3 / \text{min)} \times \text{sampling period (min)}}$$

Statistical Analysis

Results

The mean Inhalable PM in Urban area was $313.45 \pm 213.76 \text{mg}/\text{m}^3$ (104.17 – 1250.00 mg/m^3), for Rural area the mean was recorded as $200.76 \pm 116.64 \text{mg}/\text{m}^3$ (104.17-520.83 mg/m^3). The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between Urban and Rural areas with urban area clearly exceeding that of the rural area mean concentration of Inhalable particulate matter.

For the mean respirable PM in Urban area was recorded as $179.93 \pm 111.02 \text{mg}/\text{m}^3$ (104.17 – 625.0 mg/m^3), for Rural area the mean was recorded as $140.15 \pm 53.856 \text{mg}/\text{m}^3$ (104.17-312.5 mg/m^3). The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between Urban and Rural areas with urban area clearly exceeding that of the rural area mean concentration of Inhalable particulate matter.

Also, for the mean TSP concentration in Urban area was recorded as $471.64 \pm 402.13 \text{mg}/\text{m}^3$ (104.17 – 2187.50 mg/m^3), for Rural area the mean was recorded as $388.27 \pm 819.59 \text{mg}/\text{m}^3$ (104.17-416.67 mg/m^3). The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) showed a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between Urban and Rural areas with urban area clearly exceeding that of the rural area mean concentration of Inhalable particulate matter.

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of PM Concentration (mg/m^3) in Urban and Rural Areas of Nigeria.

PM	Urban	Rural
TSP	471.64±402.13	388.27±819.59
Inhalable	313.45±213.76	200.76±116.64
Respirable	179.93±111.02	140.15±53.86

Figure 2: Temporal variation of Inhalable PM over the study period

The figure 2 above shows a temporal trend in the mean Inhalable over the period of sampling. The highest mean concentration was observed in December in both Urban and rural areas. The lowest mean concentration was observed in October in the urban area, while July had the lowest concentration of Inhalable particulate matter in rural area.

Figure 3: Temporal variation of Respirable PM over the study period

The figure 3 above shows a temporal trend in the mean Respirable over the period of sampling. The highest mean concentration was observed in December in both Urban and rural areas. While the lowest mean concentration was observed in October in the both rural and urban areas.

Figure 3: Temporal variation of TSP over the study period

The figure 2 above shows a temporal trend in the mean TSP over the period of sampling. The highest mean concentration was observed in December in both Urban and rural areas. The lowest mean concentration was observed in October in the urban area, while July had the lowest concentration of TSP particulate matter in rural area.

Table 2: Comparison of Particulate matters in the two studied area.

	Urban	Rural	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio
TSP					
Above limit	73(6.4)	25(45.5)	6.65	<0.01	2.37
Below Limit	37(33.6)	30(54.5)			
Total	110(100.0)	55(100.0)			
Respirable					
Above limit	18(16.4)	1(1.8)	10.57*	<0.01	6.25
Below Limit	92(83.6)	54(98.2)			
Total	110(100.0)	55(100.0)			
Inhalable					
Above limit	55(50.0)	11(20.0)	13.75	<0.001	4.00
Below Limit	55(50.0)	44(80.0)			
Total	110(100.0)	55(100.0)			

*Yates correction applied.

The above result shows that urban areas are twice more likely to have TSP above FMEV limit than those people living in rural areas. (O.R. = 2.37 : C.I. = 1.16 – 4.84; df = 1; $\chi^2 = 6.647$; P<0.01). Considering the respirable particulate matter, it shows that urban areas are six times more likely to have respirable above FMEV limit than those people living in rural areas. (O.R. = 6.253 : C.I. = 1.57 – 448.19; df = 1; $\chi^2 = 10.57$; P<0.01). While, for inhalable, the result shows that urban areas are twice more likely to have Inhalable above FMEV limit than those people living in rural areas. (O.R. = 4 : C.I. = 1.79 – 9.44; df = 1; $\chi^2 = 13.75$; P<0.001)

Table 3: Comparison of Particulate matters in the two studied area during Dry Season.

	Urban	Rural	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio
TSP					
Above limit	44(88.0)	19(76.0)	1.79	>0.05	2.32
Below Limit	6(12.0)	6(24.0)			
Respirable					
Above limit	13 (26.0)	1(4.2)	3.96	<0.05	8.43
Below Limit	37(74.0)	24(95.8)			
Inhalable					
Above limit	37(74.0)	10(40.0)	8.24	<0.001	4.27
Below Limit	13(26.0)	15(60.0)			

Table 3: Comparison of Particulate matters in the two studied area during Wet Season.

	Urban	Rural	χ^2	p-value	Odds Ratio
TSP					
Above limit	29(48.3)	6(20.0)	6.76	<0.01	3.74
Below Limit	31(51.7)	24(80.0)			
Respirable					
Above limit	5 (8.3)	1(3.3)	3.96*	>0.05	
Below Limit	55(91.7)	29(96.7)			
Inhalable					
Above limit	18(30.0)	1 (3.3)	7.01*	<0.01	12.43
Below Limit	42(70.0)	29(96.7)			

*Yates correction applied.

Discussion

This study has shown consistencies to the fact that particulate matter is higher in rural areas than urban areas. (Jiang, et al, 2008). When this particulate matter exceeds the limit it has adverse effect on human health. Apart from the health effect of particulate matter, particulate matter also affect the visibility, inhibit photosynthesis and also cause the soiling and staining of buildings, textiles and chemical deterioration of paint (Manahan 1991, Bussotti et al 1998, Schuster et al 1994, Smith 1990, Macherizie et al 1992).

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